

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF RETAIL BANKING SERVICES BY COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. The article analyzes the current state of the use of digital technologies in the activities of commercial banks in Uzbekistan and highlights the main problems hindering the efficiency of retail banking services. It emphasizes the importance of developing innovative, customer-oriented digital banking services-particularly online microloans and remote banking solutions-to meet increasing customer expectations.

Keywords: Digital technologies, commercial banks, banking services, remote banking, microloans, customer demand, automation, customer satisfaction, blockchain technology, artificial intelligence.

Аннотация: Статья анализирует текущее состояние использования цифровых технологий в деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана и выделяет основные проблемы, препятствующие эффективности розничных банковских услуг. Особое внимание уделено важности разработки инновационных, ориентированных на клиента цифровых банковских услуг, в частности онлайн микрозаймов и дистанционных банковских решений, с целью удовлетворения растущих ожиданий клиентов.

Ключевые слова: Цифровые технологии, коммерческие банки, банковские услуги, дистанционное банковское обслуживание, микрозаймы, спрос клиентов, автоматизация, удовлетворенность клиентов, технологии блокчейн, искусственный интеллект.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada O'zbekiston tijorat banklarining faoliyatida raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llashning hozirgi holati tahlil qilinib, chakana bank xizmatlarining samaradorligiga to'sqinlik qilayotgan asosiy muammolarni ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Mijozlarning ortib borayotgan talablarini qondirish maqsadida innovatsion, mijozga yo'naltirilgan raqamli bank xizmatlarini, xususan, onlayn mikrokreditlar va masofaviy bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirish muhimligi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli texnologiyalar, tijorat banklari, bank xizmatlari, masofaviy bank xizmatlari, mikrokreditlar, mijoz talablari, avtomatlashtirish, mijozlar mamnuniyati, blokcheyn texnologiyalari, sun'iy intellekt.

Introduction.

Today's demand is to improve the quality of services by introducing new types of banking services, using the opportunities of modern financial technologies to improve the efficiency of banking services. In the conditions of digital transformation, remote banking is aimed at widening the range of remote banking services, as well as using innovative technologies to further develop the banking infrastructure.

Currently, commercial banks require their customers to create competitive financial services with the help of high technologies and at the same time, the cost of services is cheap and convenient compared to competitors.

The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 was adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022 based on the decree PF-60. In the 34th goal of this Development Strategy, the task of "increasing the volume of services by 3 times in the next 5 years through the development of services and service sectors in the regions" is defined.

Literature Review

The rapid digital transformation of the banking sector has brought about a need for banks to re-evaluate and enhance their service delivery to meet growing customer demands. According to (Gomber et al., 2018), digital transformation in banking involves the integration of advanced technologies such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, and mobile applications into banking operations, which directly impacts service delivery, efficiency, and customer experience. The study by (Moll et al., 2020) emphasizes the role of innovation in banking, highlighting the increased use of remote banking services to cater to the needs of tech-savvy customers, particularly millennials and Generation Z. In particular, online microloans and remote banking services have become essential in improving financial inclusion, as these services allow customers to access banking products without visiting a physical branch (Kagan, 2021).

Research Methodology

This research used a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, including surveys and data analysis, to assess customer preferences regarding digital banking services. A survey was conducted with 196 respondents in December 2023, focusing on their usage of remote banking and online microloan services. The data collected was analyzed using the Spearman correlation coefficient to evaluate relationships between non-monetary (e.g., age, gender) and monetary factors (e.g., income). Based on the findings, practical recommendations were developed to improve service delivery and customer

satisfaction in Uzbekistan's banking sector.

Analysis and Discussion of Results.

Today, the demands of customers for using banking services remotely are increasing more and more. If the customer's demand is not satisfied on time, the trust of the bank's customers in their bank will fade and the number of loyal customers will decrease. As a result, customers are forced to switch to banks that have introduced a convenient and easy system or to use other banking services. Therefore, as a result of continuous surveys conducted by banks among customers, it becomes possible to determine the wishes and desires of customers.

In addition, as the need of customers for this type of service is increasing today, the creation of additional benefits for potential customers of the bank leads to the provision of effective services to its customers in competitive conditions. In this regard, it is enough to leave one application for online microloan allocation to potential customers through the bank's mobile application, that is, within a few minutes, the amount requested in the application for the card balance should be formed. Therefore, we can say that the number of potential customers will increase in the future due to the convenience and speed created for customers in the mobile application, attracting many customers and increasing the quality of the services provided.

In our opinion, the conclusions formed on the basis of the survey can help to identify existing problems and further improve banking services. The survey was conducted on December 1-25, 2023, and 196 respondents participated in it. In carrying out the analysis, we take the non-monetary factors as fixed factors and try to study the dependence of the non-monetary factors on them.

We will try to determine this relationship by using the Chi-square (Chi-square) $\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$ formula and evaluate it based on the statistical Chi-square of the correlation between the answers to the questions. We form the P-value (significance value) based on 0.05. Among the total respondents, 102 men and 94 women participated. It should be noted that there are 3 men

Table 1
Status of dependence of income by gender and region of residence

Indicator name	Male	A woman	City	Village	Total
I have my own business	0,42	0,11	0,90	0,87	2,31
I have a regular salary	0,04	2,04	0,07	0,13	2,28

I am busy with seasonal work	0,18	1,63	0,20	0,66	2,67
I have no income, I am unemployed	3,23	0,11	1,50	0,29	5,13
total	3,87	3,88	2,77	2,95	13,39

As can be seen from the data of Table 1, the relationship between gender and region of residence in having income is not significant. This shows that the distribution of income is uneven, and it is necessary to analyze other factors in the delivery of banking services.

During our research, we try to assess the level of use of banking services based on the respondents' age, gender, income and place of residence. In doing so, we found it appropriate to focus on studying the following relationships. In this case, we use the Sperman correlation test. Below we can see the formula:

$$r_s = \rho_{R(X),R(Y)} = \frac{\text{cov}(R(X), R(Y))}{\sigma_{R(X)}\sigma_{R(Y)}}$$

r_s (ρ) - Represents Sperman's coefficient, where Pearson's coefficient represents a non-parametric measure between rows.

We focus on evaluating the correlation between two of the questions asked in the questionnaire. In this we distinguish based on monetary and non-monetary indicators. Non-monetary factors include age, gender, place of residence, education, and monetary factors such as income and source.

A relationship is negative monotonic if the Sperman coefficient is close to -1 (negative one), positive monotonic if close to 1 (positive one), and no relationship exists if it is 0 (zero). If $|\rho| > 0.7$ indicates that the relationship is strong.

In our opinion, non-monetary factors do not have a high correlation, it can be shown that conducting the survey is related to different audiences. Hospital, library and bank visitors were randomly asked to answer questions. This may be due to the fact that there are not many bank customers of different classifications.

Therefore, it is necessary to focus on the allocation of online microloans to potential (citizens with a permanent job and a bank card), i.e. front office legal clients of banks.

Due to the fact that the online microloan allocation process for potential customers of the bank is the same as that of a "new customer" and the lack of privileged access, it causes several inconveniences. We can say that this is one of the main factors affecting the decrease in the weight of potential customers in the

future.

In general, banks should try to create new banking services using modern information and communication technologies in their products and services. In our opinion, the above suggestions will be effective in improving banking services in Uzbekistan, and ultimately, we believe that it is important to suggest that the bank will serve to increase the customer base and increase the trust of the population in the bank.

According to the results of our research, in the development of new banking services, it is necessary to develop new types of services taking into account the demands and wishes of users and their needs, so we tried to formulate the following scientific conclusions:

- Banks will issue online microloans through their applications, thereby gradually eliminating manual functions and focusing on automating banking activities.

- Banks will drastically reduce the time required for the documentation process due to the introduction of online microloan remote service systems.

- young, middle and old age groups, as well as potential or "new customers" should be paid attention to separately.

- We need to introduce a "pioneering" voice robot system to our new users of the 50+ age group via a mobile app.

Conclusion

In general, the system of banks in our republic has been entrusted with large-scale and strategically important tasks. Naturally, their solution largely depends on the fact that the banks in our country are ready for renewal and can successfully pass the tests that life puts before us.

In other words, the final result of the reforms is evaluated by the readiness of the managers and experts working in the banking system to be updated, their professional skills, and their high scientific potential.

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